

APPLICATION OF TEAMWORK APPROACHES FOR EFFECTIVE
ACHIEVEMENT OF THE OBJECTIVES OF SECONDARY
EDUCATION IN PUBLIC SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN
RIVERS STATE

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ABSTRACT: This study examined the application of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The researcher raised two research questions and two hypotheses to guide the study. The research design selected for the study is descriptive survey. The population of the study covered all the 286 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria, comprising 7,123 teachers (2985 male teachers and 4138 female teachers, respectively). A sample of 3205 (1343 male and 1642 females) which represented 45% of the population were selected for the study. Proportionate stratified sampling technique was used to select the sample. The instrument that was used for data collection was a questionnaire designed by the researcher. It was titled 'Teamwork Approaches for Achievement of Objectives Questionnaire' (TAAOQ). Test-retest method was used to determine a reliability coefficient of is 0.82. The rating scale for answering the items on the questionnaire was a modified 4-point Likert rating scale. Weighted mean scores

and the criterion mean (2.50) were used to answer the research questions while z-test was used to test the hypotheses. The findings of the study showed the respondents agreed that the respondents agreed that the challenges implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State include; staff diversity, activities of informal groups, lack of incentives for performance, ineffective staff supervision and truancy. Sequel to the finding, it was concluded that the challenges implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State include; staff diversity, activities of informal groups, lack of incentives for performance, ineffective staff supervision and truancy. The researcher recommended that the Ministry of Education should print and distribute posters that will sensitize teachers on the value of a diverse workforce in schools.

Keywords: *Teamwork, Objectives, Secondary education, Public senior secondary schools.*

INTRODUCTION

The role of secondary education in Nigeria cannot be overemphasized. The launching of the Universal Basic Education (UBE) in 1999, by the Chief Olusegun Obasanjo administration, meant that the structure of Nigerian education system was officially changed from the 6-3-3-4 system of education to the 9-3-4. This implies that children of schooling age in Nigeria would first complete a 9 year Basic education before proceeding to secondary level of education. As shown in the 9-3-4 structure of education in Nigeria, secondary is a three year period of education and it is the second level of education and lies between the primary and tertiary levels of education. The position of secondary education in the structure of education in Nigeria makes it crucial to national development. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014) the broad objectives of secondary education include to prepare young people for integration into society – so that they can become civil and resource young adults. Also to produce learners who are ready for the pursuit of tertiary education.

Public secondary schools are founded and funded by the government to facilitate the achievement of the broad national objectives of secondary education delivery. Principals and teachers are deployed to the school to implement programmes, policies and curriculum planned for the achievement of secondary education objectives. Teachers play a critical role in the achievement of the objectives of secondary education in Nigeria. This is because they are responsible for the implementation of curriculum and other educational programmes in the classroom. Teachers are the closest school personnel to the learners – they are directly responsible for teaching and ensuring that learners learn effectively (Asodike, &Adieme, 2014). The principals on the other-hand, are responsible for harnessing resources available in schools for effective school administration and goal achievement. Ebong (2006) noted that one of the critical resources in secondary schools is the human resource (teachers). It is the duty of principals to ensure that human resource in schools is effectively utilized.

One of the ways principals can fully harness and optimize the utilization of human resources in secondary schools is by promoting teamwork approach to the implementation of school policies and programmes. Polega (2019) argued that teamwork approach towards goal achievement is the evidence of organizational workforce readiness sin the 21st Century. The need for teamwork amongst teachers cannot be overstated. Eameaim (2009) noted that teamwork is indispensable in the success of organizations seeking to improve its effectiveness and competitiveness. Teamwork approaches to the process of a work working together to complete a task and achieved shared goal. Teamwork gives members of a group opportunity to share experiences, knowledge and resources. Teamwork supports the cliché that ‘two is better than one’. It is through teamwork that organizations achieve more than they could have achieved if employees worked in isolation.

The nature of educational goals requires that members of a school should work as a team. This way, teachers can support each other, learn from each other and also help to alleviate the workload disturbances. The practice of teamwork implies that all hands must be on deck to ensure that goals are effectively achieved. Arumugam (2019) noted that teamwork approach plays an essential role of nurturing

relationships and proving motivation necessary to elicit commitment from workers in a school. Polega et al. (2019) added that there is a positive school culture and open communication in schools that adopt teamwork approach to task execution. The implication is that collaboration amongst teachers has effects on the level of teachers' morale, job satisfaction and job commitment.

Building and managing teams in organizations (like secondary school) is not an easy task. Mtawa (2013) stated that there are formidable challenges that mitigate principals' efforts towards institutionalizing a culture of teamwork in amongst school personnel. Pitsoe and Isingoma (2021) argued that teachers tend to work in isolation rather than as a team and this poses a challenge for principals seeking to instill a culture of team approach in achieving shared objectives. There is wide-range of observable hurdles that principals seeking to instill a culture of teamwork approach in schools, often faces. One of such challenges is the wide-range of individual differences which exist amongst teachers. Individual differences existing amongst a group of employees is form what is known as staff diversity. The diversities include area of specialization, age, sex, status, skill set, and others. No two people are alike – everyone is unique in one form or the other (Amorim, 2018).

Transitioning from individual work approach to teamwork approach toward goal achievement is a hurdle that school principals are meant to face. Not all individuals would want to look beyond individuals differences and collaborate with others. Sadly, unless school principals effectively instill a culture of respect and value for individual differences, the diversity existing amongst teachers continue to be a source of discrimination, tension and conflict (Vangrieken, 2013). Another significant challenge appears to be informal group activities. No principal can completely annihilate the existence of informal groups (Okorie, 2009). Although such groups are easily disruptive, they meet teachers' social needs and serve as a source of grapevine. However, very powerful informal groups could undermine principals' efforts towards unifying all and sundry in the school. If a principal fails to infiltrate informal groups and get them to work with other individuals who are not members of such informal groups, the result could be failure to unify the entire workforce to work as a team.

Abraham (2003) identified the role of motivation in facilitating teamwork approach in tasks execution in schools. He concluded that timely and adequate payment of teachers' remuneration and other incentives would foster the spirit of teamwork. One of the main functions of reward is to raise teachers' morale and commitment. An unmotivated teacher would not care about a team. When teachers do not feel adequately motivated, their attitude to work becomes negative. For instance, they might begin to exhibit attitude of gross absenteeism from school, lateness or other forms of truancy. A teacher who is often late and absent from school cannot be abatable to work with other teachers. Polega et. al. (2019) found principals' leadership style as another factor that could hinder effective teambuilding. Abraham (2003) noted that principals' leadership style can affect teachers' perception of principals, school climate and nature of communication. Where there is no communication, there would be no teamwork. While no single leadership style is considered the best for school administration, some educationists have argued that principals should endeavor to adopt the democratic style of leadership because it increases trust, communication and collaboration.

Secondary school principals have the reasonability of ensuring that teamwork approach is adopted for the pursuit of goal achievement in the schools. Consequently, they must adopt different strategies that will create conducive school environment where teamwork approach can thrive unhindered. Polega (2019) argued that principals can create a culture of teamwork by designing events that will bring teachers together to improve trust, openness, and social bond. Such events might include weekend hangouts, get-together, and recreation activities or picnics. These events are primarily for socialization. However, they are capable of enabling teachers to interact and build relationships that will improve the quality of teamwork. Hallinger (2005) added that strategically grouping teachers into small groups with significant diversity can improve team quality and make a team stronger.

Eameaim J., et al. (2009) argued that large teams appear to be more difficult to manage than small teams – thus, the strategy of breaking a large group into small groups can prove effective for improving teamwork within large groups. School weekly roaster is a form of small grouping of member a school. Furthermore, the

different small group committees are also example of the use of small groups in schools. The extent, to which small groups in schools can promote teamwork approach, might depend on principals' ability to sensitize each team to prioritize the strength of their teams, rather than individual performances. Another strategy for strengthening teamwork approach towards effective goals achievement is the practice of rewarding team performance (Hargreaves, 1994).

While it is group to reward astounding individual's performances, the culture of rewarding team performance will go a long way to reinforce the value and culture of teamwork. For instance, at the end of a term, the principal can reward the best performing group on the weekly roaster, the best adhoc committee at the end of the execution of an inert-house sports event or the best performing department at the end of a term. These rewards will make the recognized team proud and also challenge other teams to improve upon their previous performance. Eameaim J., et al. (2009) concluded that prioritizing the rewarding of team effort will improve collaborations in a social system (like schools). Decision making process can make or mar a team. Okorie (2009) explained that democratic process of decision often encourages team building. The first requirement for team building is to show respect and regard for every member of a team. This practice begins with communicating clearly that everyone's uniqueness is recognized and everyone's opinion matters.

Several educationists have noted that teachers' commitment towards the implementation of school programmes and policies is higher when they participate improves of decision making or policy formulation (Abraham, 2003). Coetze and Pauw (2013) advocated that principals should not micromanaged teachers and committees set-up in the school. This implies that principals should not make all the decisions – teachers and groups should be allowed the space and freedom to make decisions regarding how to execute tasks. Essentially, this could enhance the confidence of individuals and teams working in the school and consequently, increase their morale and commitment.

It appears that educational stakeholders are clamoring for the application of teamwork approach towards effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools. However, the challenges and needs to

be clearly identified and understood. Furthermore, the task before secondary school principals is to develop and implement strategies that would improve teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools. It is sequel to this backdrop that this study examined the application of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Teachers perform critical roles in secondary education delivery. This meant that the success or failure of secondary school delivery may be largely determined by teachers' performance. Teachers' performance in schools can be achieved through teachers working in isolation or as a team. Educationists have continued to clamour for the institutionalizing teacher teamwork approach towards achieving the goals of secondary education in Rivers State. What bothers the researcher is that despite the reforms in secondary education delivery, the outcome of secondary education continues to fall below expectation. The cause of this publicly known situation remains uncertain as several factors have been considered to likely cause the widespread examination malpractice, quality of secondary school leavers, high teacher job dissatisfaction and other negative indicators of poor secondary school delivery.

It appears that no known empirical study has determined whether or not teamwork approach is widely adopted in schools for achievement of objectives. Also, the challenging of institutionalizing teamwork approach as well as strategies for improving the implementation of teamwork approach for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education appears to have not been investigated empirically. It is sequel to this backdrop and the gap identified that this study will examine the application of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to assess the application of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior

secondary schools in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of the study will include to:

1. Find out the challenges of implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. Determine the strategies adopted for improving the implementation of teamwork approaches effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

1. What are the challenges of implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
2. What are the strategies adopted for improving the implementation of teamwork approaches effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and each was tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the challenges of implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the strategies for improving the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Significance of the Study

This study is significant to teachers, principals, policy makers and other researchers. This study will be useful to teachers as it will further enhance teachers' understanding of the challenges of implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools. Technically, the study will also equip teachers to collaborate with their colleagues and school administrators to tackle such challenges. The study will also benefit school principals as it will further enlighten them on the strategies they can adopt to effectively implement teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools.

Secondary school principals will also find the study useful as its findings and recommendations will serve as a working document to guide principals reviews and decision making on implementation of teamwork approaches for the effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools. Finally, the study will be useful to other researchers as it will serve as source of conceptual and empirical literature for further related studies.

Theoretical Framework

Social Interdependence Theory provided theoretical framework for this study. The theory was formulated by Morton Deutsch in his 1949 work. The work is titled 'A Theory of Co-operation and Competition'. The Social Interdependence Theory was an expansion of Kurt Lewin's earlier concepts of group dynamics. The Social Interdependence Theory explains how goal structures predict interpersonal interactions amongst members of a social unit. The underlining assumption of the Social Interdependence Theory is that there is a difference between positive interdependence (cooperation) and negative interdependence (competition). The Social Interdependence Theory explains that if goals of individuals are linked, they would cooperate to achieve them. Also, if individuals held accountable for their contributions towards achieved group goals, there would be increased cooperation amongst members of the group.

The Social Interdependence Theory is relevant to this study because it can be applied to all social systems, including schools. Several educationists have maintained that school is a social system with interrelated parts. These parts are expected to work together in order for the goals of the school to be achieved. The Social Interdependence Theory offers framework for developing teamwork approaches in schools. In line with the theory, schools can achieve teamwork approaches by linking goals of individual teachers and goals of the different units of the school in order to promote cooperation (teamwork). Furthermore, individual accountability of teachers can enhance teamwork approach in schools. By applying Social Interdependence Theory to this study, the challenges and strategies for implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of goals can be empirically examined.

Review of Related Empirical Studies

Osondu (2020) examined the implications of teamwork approach in effective public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The study examined principal staff management strategies and effective administration in public secondary schools in Rivers State. To achieve the purpose of the study, the researcher formulated three objectives of the study, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The study made use of descriptive survey design for the research design. The population of the study consists of all the principals and vice principals in the 24 public secondary schools in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area with a population size of 72 principals and teachers. The study made use of multistage sampling technique for the sampling technique with a sample size of 72. The study made use of structured questionnaire for the instrument for data collection. The items were ranked or weighted as Strongly Agree, Agree, Disagree and Strongly Disagree.

The data gathered were analyzed using mean and standard deviation while the null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistical tool at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the analysis, the findings of the study revealed that good principals' teamwork management enhances effective administration by improving productivity and quality decision-making. It was recommended that Ministry of Education should organize workshops to equip principals with teamwork management skills. This

previous study is related to the present study because it identifies teamwork as a critical issue in school system. It also shows that the management of teamwork could have implications in quality of delivery and outcomes in public senior secondary schools. The gap found in this previous study is that, it failed to examine how teamwork could affect the achievement of objectives of secondary education. Sequel to this, this present study will examine application of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

In a related study, Mutimba and Moi, (2013) examined the impact of teamwork on academic performance of students in Kenyan Secondary schools of Kajiado County. A descriptive design was used in the research study. It targeted a population of 30 administrators, 50 H.O. D's & D.O. S's, 100 teachers and 150 students. The sample population was achieved through use of simple random sampling technique. Data was collected from the respondents through the use of a questionnaire. Analysis of the data was then done using qualitative content analysis for qualitative data whereas quantitative data was presented using SPSS. Inferential data analysis was used to make general conclusions for a large population whereas multiple regression model was used for regression analysis. In conclusion, the researcher explored how team work influenced academic performance of secondary schools in Kajiado County.

From the findings, team work greatly had an effect on academic performance of secondary schools in Kajiado County. There was a positive correlation with influence of team work having the highest correlation of 0.780. This previous study is relevant to the present study because it identifies that teamwork can affect students' performance. The finding of this previous study is related to the present study because it shows researchers in the field of education are interested in school administration. The gap found in the previous study is that it was not delimited to cover public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The present study will fill this gap.

In a related study Ogunsakin (2024) examined teamwork, team leadership and school organization performance in Lagos State University. The purpose of this paper is to show the underlying link between teamwork, team leadership and school

organizational performance in Nigeria. This study is anchored on linkage model by Wright (2003). The study adopted descriptive correlational design type. A sample of 3 teams were drawn from each of the five randomly selected faculties in Lagos state University, Ojo, using convenience sampling and stratified random sampling techniques. The size of each team ranges from 6 to 10. The sample size, of 200 respondents (from 15 teams), comprising Heads of Departments (HODs) as the team leaders and their members of staff as team members, using a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. All variables were measured with validated instruments in a four-point Likert scale.

The reliability of the instrument (0.68) is measured using Chronbach Alpha. Data obtained were analysed using simple percentage for the research questions, while Chi Square and multiple regression analyses were used to verify the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0. The inferential results show $R=0.808$ indicating a strong positive impact of the predictors (Teamwork, Team leader) on the response variable (Organational performance) and $R^2=0.606$ indicating that 60.6 percent of the variation in the dependent variables can be explained by the independent variable. Also, the F-value showed that overall regression model is statistically significant and valid for any predictive purposes. Equally, the coefficients of the individual predictors of team members' and team leader's performance and their t-values showed varying degrees of positive relationship with the dependent variable.

It was concluded from this study that school organizational performance depends upon the positive interrelationship within teams; between teams and team leaders; and between team leaders and their super-ordinates for teamwork to be effectively performed and that a well composed team with an appropriate team leader can influence the success and the growth of both the organization and teamwork. Consequently, it was recommended among others that school managers or owners should provide the necessary atmosphere, skills and tools that will enhance teamwork effectiveness. The study also recommends that team members should be allowed to select their team leaders who they can work with in order to enhance organizational productivity. This previous study is related to the previous study

because it identifies teamwork as a variable for assessing performance in schools. It also provides literature for the present study. However, the previous study contains gaps that will be filled in the present study. One of such gaps is that it is the previous study was not delimited to consist public secondary schools in Rivers State.

Methodology

The research design used in this study was descriptive survey. The population of the study covered all the 286 public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria, comprising 7,123 teachers (2985 male teachers and 4138 female teachers, respectively). A sample of 3205 (1343 male and 1642 females) which represented 45% of the population were selected for the study. Proportionate stratified sampling technique was used to select the sample. The instrument that was used for data collection was a questionnaire designed by the researcher. It was titled 'Teamwork Approaches for Achievement of Objectives Questionnaire' (TAAOQ). Test-retest method was used to determine a reliability coefficient of is 0.82. The rating scale for answering the items on the questionnaire was a modified 4-point Likert rating scale.

Weighted mean scores and the criterion mean (2.50) were used for data analysis. Specifically, if a questionnaire item has a weighted mean score that was equal to, or greater than 2.50, the remarked assigned to it was 'agreed' while questionnaire items with weighted mean scores that are less than 2.50 were assigned 'disagreed' as its remark. z-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. When the z-calculated score is greater than the z-table score, the null hypothesis is considered significant but when the z-calculated score is less than the z-table score, the null hypothesis is considered not significant.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the challenges of implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of the responses of Male and Female Teachers on the Challenges of Implementing Teamwork Approaches for Effective Achievement of the Objectives of Secondary Education in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/NO.	ITEMS	WEIGHTED MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	REMARK
1.	Staff demographic diversity (age, gender, ethnicity, socio-economic) in my school impedes the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education	3.47	2.03	Agreed
2.	Activities of informal groups in my school create division and impedes the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education	2.89	1.78	Agreed
3.	The leadership style of my principal impedes the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education	2.01	1.07	Disagreed
4.	Lack of incentives for performance impedes the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education	2.99	2.33	Agreed
5.	Ineffective staff supervision hinders the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education	2.97	2.33	Agreed
6.	Staff truancy impedes the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education	2.90	2.01	Agreed
Criterion Mean = 2.50				

Data on Table 1 showed that the respondents agreed that items 1, 2, 3, 5 and 6 have weighted mean scores (3.47, 2.89, 2.99, 2.97 and 2.90, respectively) higher than the criterion mean (2.50). Thus, the respondents agreed that items 1, 2, 3, 5 and 6 are the challenges implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Table 1 also showed that item the weighted mean score of item 4 (2.01) is lower than the weighted mean score (2.50). Thus, the respondents agreed that item 4 is not one of the challenges implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: What are the strategies for improving the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Scores of the responses of Male and Female Teachers on the Strategies for Improving the Implementing Teamwork Approaches for Effective Achievement of the Objectives of Secondary Education in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

S/NO.	ITEMS	WEIGHTED MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION	REMARK
7.	My principals uses democratic decision making style to improve the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education	3.09	2.19	Agreed
8.	My principals uses multiple methods of communication (one-on-one, social media and grapevine) to improve the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education	3.00	2.01	Agreed
9.	My principal uses multiple meeting locations			

	(within and outside) the school to improve the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education	2.11	1.03	Disagreed
10.	My principal periodically rotates positions in order to improve the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education	2.69	2.38	Agreed
11.	My principal periodically reshuffles team compositions in order to improve the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education	2.00	1.07	Disagreed
12.	My principal rewards teams based on merit in order to improve the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education	2.34	1.02	Disagreed
13.	My principal initiates staff leisure (informal) engagements in order to improve the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education	2.08	1.02	Disagreed
Criterion Mean = 2.50				

Data on Table 2 showed that the respondents agreed that items 7, 8, 10 and 11 have weighted mean scores (3.09, 3.00 and 2.69 respectively) higher than the criterion mean (2.50). Thus, the respondents agreed that items 7, 8, 10 and 11 are the strategies for improving the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. However, Table 2 further revealed that, items 9, 11, 12 and

13 have mean scores (2.11, 2.00, 2.34 and 2.08, respectively) that are less than the criterion mean (2.50). Thus, the respondents disagreed that items 9, 11, 12 and 13 are the strategies for improving the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the challenges of implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: z-test on there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the challenges of implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State

RESPONDENTS	N	\bar{x}	SD	Z-CRIT. SCORE	Z-CAL. SCORE	df	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE	RESULT
Male Teachers	1343	3.68	2.07	1.96	0.85	3203	0.05	Not significant
Female Teachers	1642	3.66	2.03					

Table 3 showed that the z-calculated value of 712 degree of freedom, at 0.05 level of significance was 0.85, against the z-criterion value of 1.96. Sequel to this, the null hypotheses stating that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the challenges of implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State was retained.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the strategies for improving the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: z-test on there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the strategies for improving the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

RESPONDENTS	N	\bar{x}	SD	Z-CRITERIAL SCORE	Z-CALCULATED SCORE	df	LEVEL OF SIGNIFICANCE	RESULT
Male Teachers	1343	3.68	2.07	1.96	0.83	3203	0.05	Not significant
Female Teachers	1642	3.66	2.03					

Table 3 showed that the z-calculated value of 712 degree of freedom, at 0.05 level of significance was 0.83, against the z-criterion value of 1.96. Sequel to this, the null hypotheses stating that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the challenges of implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State was retained.

Discussion of Findings

Challenges of Implementing Teamwork Approaches for Achievement of Objectives

The findings on Table 1 revealed that the respondents agreed that the challenges implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State include; staff diversity, activities of informal groups, lack of incentives for performance,

ineffective staff supervision and truancy. This finding is in tandem with the assertion of Ossai (2025) that staff diversity can be a blessing and curse school administrators – they can improve quality of staff and outside, while at the same time they could be a source of conflict, discrimination and job disengagement. In line with this assertion, Stoner, et. al. (1995) argued that staff diversity is an asset, only when managers understand the need for integration, justice and respect for individual difference.

Bello (2013) added that If not properly managed, staff diversity could impede open communication, trust, mutual respect and collaboration. This implies that staff diversity can indeed pose a challenge for implementation of teamwork approaches in school administration. There is hardly a public senior secondary school that does not have features of staff diversity. Chiefly amongst them appears to be gender, age, ethnicity, years of experience, rank, religion, technology proficiency, etc. The need to give critical attention to issues bothering around staff diversity in public senior secondary schools cannot be overemphasized. In line with the findings, Okorie (2009) pointed out that the activities of informal groups in schools can be both beneficial and destructive in school administration.

While informal group activities could meet the social and welfare needs of staff members, it could lead to divisions – a ‘we’ vs. ‘them’ situation – that could hinder trust, open communication and teamwork. Abraham (2003) opined that no school administrator can completely purge a school of informal groups; however rules and regulations can be used to checkmate their activities in the school. Rather than try to clampdown on the existence and activities of informal groups, school administrators should find innovative ways of harnessing the usefulness of such groups. If well managed, informal groups and their characteristic grapevine channel of communication can be used to improve teamwork in schools.

In tandem with the finding, Ebong (2006) stated that one of the challenges of public secondary administration in Nigeria is the lack of availability of resource to provide monetary and non-, monetary incentives to staff members. The government at all levels has failed to issue impress funds to school principals even though they have continued to insist that public secondary education in nation should be free and

compulsory (Nwakpa, 2016). It appears therefore that no matter how effective and efficient teachers work, principals are unable to provide some form of monetary or material incentives, because of lack of impress. Despite the failure of government to provide impress to principals, some secondary school principals find it difficult to utilize funds generated internally to motivate teachers and encourage teamwork. Such principals fail to realize that it is the collective performance of the teachers that is responsible for the effectiveness of the school and the generation of internal revenue for the school.

Agiah (2019), supervision in public senior secondary school appears to be a mere academic activity. Asodike and Adieme (2014) argued that supervision exercises in secondary schools is even counterproductive because it is perceived to be witch hunt or a mere academic routine where supervisors merely assess teachers' notes, diaries and registers. Little or no effort is made to interact with teachers in order to indentify the challenges that meet on the job and how to help them resolve such challenges. Teacher truancy has remained one of the most predominant challenges of managing schools (Edem, 2006). In public schools, teacher truancy appears to be high because the teachers appear to either have political godfathers or believe that the process of suspending or sacking them is not an easy one. Neither principals nor school supervisors have the power to punish or sack a teacher who is perceives to be affiliated to top politicians. In line with the finding, Obasi and Asodike (2017) pointed out that teacher truancy leads to human resource wastage in schools. It also leads to weakened team work – non-truant teachers end up feeling discouraging knowing that truant teachers receive their salary even without working. Adams's Equity Theory, employees would intentionally reduce their performance to match the performance of other employees who earn more or same remuneration for less work-done.

Table 1 also showed that the respondents agreed that principals' leadership style is not one of the challenges of implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education. This finding agreed with the assertion of Abraham (2003) that there is no one perfect leadership style for all situation. He noted that principals must choose a leadership style that matches the

needs, challenges, aspirations and attitude of teachers. In line with the findings, Okorie (2009) maintained that principals' leadership style can make or mar a school. Thus, principals must pay attention to adopting only a leadership style that could promote effective school administration and teambuilding. No matter what leadership style a principal picks, it is important for school principals to ensure that it does not hinder open communication, trust and team approach towards achieving the objectives of secondary schools in Nigeria.

Table 3 revealed that the null hypotheses stating that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the challenges of implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State was retained.

Strategies for Improving Teamwork Approaches for Achievement of the Objectives

The findings on Table 2 revealed that the respondents agreed that the strategies adopted for improving the implementation of teamwork approaches effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State include; use of democratic decision making style, use of multiple methods of communication (one-on-one, social media and grapevine) and periodical rotation of positions. This finding agreed with the position of Abraham (2003) that democratic process of decision making increase trust, participation and teamwork. Everyone gets a sense of belonging when decisions are democratically made, consequently, there is high level of cooperation when it comes to implementation of such decisions. Okorie (2009) opined that people should be engaged in the process of making a decision that will directly or indirectly affect them, as well require their involvement in its implementation.

A democratic process of decision making increases communication in an organization (Gemechu, 2014). Edem (2006), stated that communication is more efficient in schools where the leadership is democratic. In line with the finding, Addai (2013) argued that use of multiple methods of communication increase communication amongst leadership and personnel. It also suits the different needs of personnel. For instance, some employees would make more active and vocal when

meetings are held virtually via chat, voice calls or video calls – such employees may be less engaging during live face-to-face meetings. Furthermore, the use of alternative methods of communication could save time, reduce too frequent physical meetings and give room for conversations to continue after a meeting might have ended. One of the advantages of holding virtual meetings is that participants and members who were not live during the meeting can go back and review that contents and exchanges during the meeting, as well as make their own input at a later time.

It is observed that most organizations have WhatsApp groups created to enhance communication amongst members of the organization or departments. Such groups also encourage formal and informal interactions. Such interactions are likely to increase teamwork amongst employees. Similarly, in line with the findings Hargreaves (1994) mused that positions in organizations should be rotated periodically to give everyone a sense of belonging and encourage individuals to make their unique contributions. In secondary schools, principals often appoint Departmental Heads, Heads of standing and adhoc committees, Form masters and mistresses, Inter-House Sports House masters and mistresses, staff secretary, etc. Unless, these positions are rotated and every teacher knows they can be appointed into any of these positions on a rotational basis, some teachers might feel it is the birthright of others. When this becomes the feeling of majority of the teachers, they might become disengaged from the non-statutory duties in the school.

Consequently, the level of teamwork in the school would decline. Arumugam (2019), noted that the practice of rotating appointments would increase and diversify the experiences and competence of staff members, give employees opportunities to face new frontier of on-the job learning and development. Irrespective of ethnicity, sex, status or experience, every teacher should be given an opportunity occupy leadership positions in schools. Table 2 also showed that the respondents disagreed that the following are the strategies adopted for improving the implementation of teamwork approaches effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State include; use of multiple meeting locations (within and outside), rewarding teams based on merit and initiates staff leisure (informal) engagements.

In line with the finding Maduagwu and Nwogu (2006) (2019) noted that organizational leadership should be dynamic in management of meetings – this includes choosing a location where meetings are held. Public secondary schools do not have boardrooms. Consequently, meetings are often held in a designated staffroom that is spacious to accommodate participants or in principals' offices. Employees have different needs, interests and motivators. The environment where meetings are held could affect the morale and participation of employees. The more people are excited about participating in a meeting; it is likely that the team will become more effective. Leisure and work-life balance are almost inseparable. In line with the finding, Egu (2013) noted that there is need for schools to have recreational facilities where teachers could engage in recreational activities to improve the quality of their physical, mental and emotional health while pursuing work-life balance.

Principals who imitate get together, mini celebrations and other leisure activities are likely to achieve higher level of team cohesion (if all things are equal). Table 4 showed that the null hypotheses stating that there is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female teachers on the challenges of implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State was retained.

Conclusion

Following the findings of the study, it was concluded that the challenges implementing teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State include; staff diversity, activities of informal groups, lack of incentives for performance, ineffective staff supervision and truancy. Furthermore, it was concluded that secondary school principals are utilizing various strategies to improve the implementation of teamwork approaches for effective achievement of the objectives of secondary education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Recommendations

1. The Ministry of Education should print and distribute to schools, posters that will sensitize teachers on the value of a diverse workforce.

2. Principals should ensure that the composition of committees in their schools reflects staff diversity.
3. The State Government should make budgetary provision for an impress to be given to principals to enable them provide incentives for individuals and teams that are astounding in the school.
4. The Ministry of Education should train and retrain school supervisors on how to effectively supervise teachers for improvement in team approach to goal achievement.
5. The School Based Management Committee (SBMC) should be given the power to suspend teachers known for truancy.
6. Principals should rotate the venue of meetings held in the school.
7. Principals should initiate programs that will improve leisure amongst teachers.

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